

THE IMPLICATION OF HIGH-STAKES TESTING TO PRIMARY AND SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN KENYA

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Abstract:

High stakes testing involves attaching consequences (stakes) to test scores. This in education implies that the teacher and students will automatically be held accountable of their performance. Globally high stakes testing is the operational system because most states have resorted to standards which are only achievable with monitoring of education operations. The danger however could be the effects it might have on teaching and learning. This researcher set out to establish the context, form or nature of high stakes testing, what educators and even the student think about it. The research further determined the implications it has on teaching and the Kenya education process. In a nutshell, this study was to determine how high stakes testing affects what the teachers teach and how they teach. This research design was quantitative and qualitative, targeting teachers in both primary and secondary schools in the Kakamega district and also expose facto to establish the cause and effect of high-stakes testing from researches by the American Research Association (2002) and other relevant studies in the area of testing. The results were such that the teachers indicated that tests were used for accountability purposes causing them to teach to the test in the later classes. However, most teachers agreed that high-stakes tests were necessary to maintain standards. The students argued that there is need to review the global trends as well as nature of assessment in Kenya so that tests are not used as a mechanism in a single defined assessment and a consequence for pass and failure, it is time to tailor exams to contribute to performance towards socio-economic equitable and performance related conditions.

Keywords: high-stakes testing, primary schools, secondary schools, Kenya

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1. Background of the study

High-stakes testing is a word derived from 'stake' to mean, "something at stake" thus consequences for failing and passing. High-stake testing would therefore mean that when an examinee passes the test, there are certain benefits such as high school certificate or diploma, scholarship, entry to university, license to practice or many other rewards. The vice versa would also mean high-stakes testing. *"Tests can provide information that facilitates and supports decision making particularly in the domain of education. However, each type of interest from test data, and each model of decision making carries with it certain constraints and risks"* (Gifford 1986). In this case, we can talk of the various types of assessment and the purpose of each. When you ask a question: of what intent an examination, the answer lies in the purpose for which the test data will be put.

High-stakes testing is a controversial issue in education and met with a lot of argument both for and against it. Proponents of high-stakes testing argue that learners and teachers need a drive, a reward or a motivating factor to work towards. Diane Ravitch claims that high-stakes are important in maintaining standards, Roderic (2002). They (proponents) also argue that stakes help administrators and teachers to monitor educational programs. Perhaps there is need to establish whether high-stakes improve student learning and educational standards. A study with Massachusetts teachers of English indicates that high-stakes is important in allowing everyone to be part of a national conversation about testing. The other stake in testing is the low stakes testing, a system evident in some policy framework but not as common lately as the high-stakes. We need to understand that in various contexts with high-stakes, low-stakes could not suffice. A study was carried out in Ireland that had a purely low-stakes testing system.

Then there need to be a strike of balance between low-stakes and high-stakes. The question of fatigue to the learner and teacher arises in high-stakes. Therefore, high-stakes testing is characteristic of three things. *"A single defined assessment, a clear line drawn between those who pass and those who fail and a consequence for passing or failing."* (Gifford, 1986).

Although high-stakes deny diversification in teaching and learning, they are inevitable because all stakeholders must take part in conversation about testing, meaning that discussion, decision and sanctions will have to be attached to test scores. A controversy exists that testing is essential in education. The test is the best device used to obtain measurement. *"The test has been shown to be of greater practical utility than most other procedures"* (Linderman, 1971) Public examinations are used for certification, placement, motivation among other things, implying that they determine mobility. This is a heavy reward attached to the test hence high stakes in Kenya's public examination. High stakes testing could also arise as a result of using test results to make decisions about the teacher. Decisions on promotion of the teacher, disciplining, demotion, in which school the teacher be are among many decisions that can be made from test results.

This raises stakes, thereby affecting pedagogy, curriculum, learning and classroom practice in general. Consideration should be made when lamping schools

together for rewards and decision, because public examination become high stakes when norm referencing is key. Schools would do anything to get a name among the top. When the mean (norm) becomes the issue and accountability decisions or any other made, it raises the stakes. In ranking, consideration in terms of resources, learner's entry behavior, and teacher experience should be made. In conclusion, whether high stakes create a relationship between excellence and competence needs to be investigated. It is also important for educators to gain knowledge and insight on what high stakes testing is and how it impacts to both the teacher and the learner. This study explored the impact of high stakes testing in order to shed light into the ensuing debates and challenges with the subject that touch on the impact of assessment and test implementation over a wide range of variables.

2. Statement of the problem

Globally, standards in education are the concern of every nation. Standards can easily be attained when educators make decisions on the basis of the score on the test. With this, stake holders in education are becoming part of the great debate resulting from high stakes testing, which is totally a contentious issue: and has spark mixed opinion hence opponents and proponents. Since there already are rewards attached to test scores from K.C.P.E and K.C.S.E, we establish whether holding the teacher accountable had any effects to teaching and learning.

2.1 Objectives of the study

- To establish the implications of high stakes regarding Kenya Education Assessment.

2.2 Significance of the study

The study would guide policy because it was bound to reveal the effect of high stakes on teaching and learning, thereby assisting in regulating rewards and decisions made on test scores. The study would also enable stakeholders and the Kenya National Examinations Council contextualizes the cause of cheating in national and public examinations. Research indicates that states with high stake have faced problems.

3. Literature Review

3.1 The Rise of High-stakes Testing: A Historical Perspective

There were several effects of high – stakes testing, for instance, in the 1980s there was a dramatic increase in test scores hence “test score inflation” thus test scores accelerated without corresponding student learning. This led to the joint establishment of standards by the American Educational Research Association (AERA), American Psychological Association (APA), and the National Council on Measurements in Education (NCME). The convention came up with 12 conditions to be met to ensure sound implementation of high–stakes educational testing programmes. The conditions addressed test

development, scaling scoring, and measures of reliability, validity and fairness. Seven principles were developed by over 80 national and regional education and civil rights organization to change testing practice to be helpful to student learning. Benard Gifford in his study in Ireland contrasts high – stakes testing to low stakes testing and says that *“a low stakes testing program in contrast to high – stakes program is one where people do not perceive the important rewards or sanctions are tied directly to test performance. In such programs, results are reported to teachers but there is no immediate automatic decision linked to performance.”* Gifford (1986). The vice versa defines high-stakes testing as a context where decisions, rewards and sanctions about individuals and basis of test scores as instructional decisions, licensure and employment decisions and program evaluation decisions become critical, tests become high – takes.

3.2 Context, Proponents and Opponents of High stakes Testing

A. Testing Defined

Madaus (1988) defines a high stakes test as a sample of items used to make influences on decisions or descriptions about people or institutions relative to some domain. Peter W. Arisian (1988) says high stakes refer to when an important consequence that is a high stake such as receiving a high school diploma or a teaching certificate is tied to test performance.

Tests are used to communicate the management of schools creating sanctions. This is another high- stakes context. High-stakes also exists in contexts where graduation or promotion decisions, teacher evaluation, merit pay allocation, awarding of compensatory funds are made on the basis of the test scores. Therefore according to Gifford (1986) *“Examples of high-stakes include linking standardized test scores to such important decision as (1) graduation from high school, promotion from grade to grade sometimes called ‘gates’ or automatic placement in a remedial program (2) the evaluation of teachers or administrators (3) the awarding of merit pay, or promotion to the status of master teacher and (4) The allocation of resources to schools”*. Generally high – stakes situations occur in contexts where test scores are used to make critical decisions about individuals and school or institutions; and reform education. Policy issues are assessed for school accountability purposes thereby making tests high stakes.

B. Proponents of High Stakes Testing

Proponents of measurement driven instruction argue that teaching to the test is a virtue. Thus, if the test measures basic skills then preparing students for the skills by the test will improve basic skills Madaus F. (1988). Melisa Roderick et al (2003) indicates that proponents of high stakes testing argue that such policies will motivate students to work harder and parents to monitor their child’s progress. They also argue that it will benefit low achieving students and that it also sets standards to provide extra support for students because it will provide incentives for hard work and incentives for special attention by teachers.

C. Opponents of High Stake testing

Crighton (2003) argues that tests for school effectiveness ignore other factors that contribute to performance like socio economic environment and physical conditions; it

leads to narrowing of the curriculum because of neglect of non-examinable subjects, makes teachers focus on border line students and it results to “ghettoization” in schools where parents are encouraged to support schools. Don Zancarella (1992) argues that high stakes interface with the decision making of individual teachers and schools, as cited from Madaus (1988) leads to a curriculum that focuses on the most testable. Luna et al (2001) identifies the critics of high stakes testing as Susan Ohanian who argues that such tests will reinforce rather than ameliorate inequities in education.

David McClelland and John Atkinson in achievement motivation argue that “*people who strive for excellence in a field for the sake of achieving*”.

The second principle by Donald Campbell explains why high – stakes result to malpractice like cheating in examination and others. The principle states that the more any quantitative social indicator is used for social decision making, the more likely it will be to distort and corrupt the social process it is intended to monitor. This is distortion. Closely related to the third principle which explains the reason why teachers teach to the test. It states that if important decisions are presumed to be related to test result, then teachers will teach to the test. The fourth principle explains how teachers corrupt skills and drill examinees. This de facto defines the curriculum as indicated by the principle which states: In every setting where a high stakes test operates, a tradition of past test develops which eventually de facto defines the curriculum.

The fifth principle states that teachers pay particular attention to the form of the questions on a high – stakes test, for example short answer, essay, and multiple choices and adjust their instruction accordingly. The principle explains why there is narrowing of the curriculum hence the effect of high–stakes to teaching.

The sixth principle states: when test results are the sole or even partial arbiter of future educational or life choices, society tends to treat test results as the major goal of schooling rather than as a useful but fallible indicator of achievement.

4. The Kenya Education Assessment System

Education in Kenya traces its origin from colonialism. The education offered by the British system was biased, because offered it was to fulfill the selfish and racist objectives of the colonialists. At independence in 1963, the Ominde report reformed education to suit African needs. Many reforms have taken place to today including the changes in the education structure from 7.6.3.2 to 8.4.4 as indicated by the Mackay report, Eshiwani (1993).

Assessment in Kenya started early from the colonial system to the East African examinations called East African Certificate of Education (EACE) at O’ level and the East African Advanced Certificate of Education at A’ level. Kenya thereafter decentralized control of examinations from the common East Africa to Kenya solely. The Kenya Advanced Certificate of Education (KACE) was done at A’ level and the Certificate for Primary Education (CPE) done at grade seven in primary school. Changes in the curriculum were undertaken and the structure changed from the 7:4:2:3

to the 8:4:4 resulting to the current examinations, KCSE at the end of the secondary course and KCPE at the end of the primary course Eshiwani G S (1993).

KNEC administers public examinations with the purpose of:

- Selection of students for educational opportunities thus university and secondary.
- Certification
- Curriculum control

KNEC measures achievement by converting test scores to letter grades at KCSE thus: Grade A the highest with 12 points, A minus, B plus, B plain, B minus, C plus, C plain, C minus, D plus, D plain, D minus and the lowest grade E with 1 point. KCPE is currently ranked at the highest total mark of 500 in the five subjects examined.

The KNEC act mandates the Kenya National Examination Council to conduct examination for Kenya primary, Secondary schools and tertiary institutions. Kenya has once undertaken national assessment as a participant in the Southern and Eastern Africa Consortium for Monitoring Education Quality. (Juliana Nzomo et al) The assessment targets class six for baseline data on the essential features of the school system.

5. Research Design and Methodology

This was a survey research, an ex post facto research designs were used to investigate possible and describe cause and effect relations by observing existing condition or state of affairs and searching back in time for plausible causal factors. Cohen Loves (1980)

5.1 Sample for data collection

The research targeted twenty-five 25 secondary school teachers, 25 primary school teachers, and 25 secondary school students. To get data on the implications of assessment vis a vis content analysis, 5 scholars or specialists in testing (psychometrics) formed part of the sample. Both levels (primary and secondary) were relevant in the research because the exams done at both primary (K.C.P.E) and in secondary (K.C.S.E) are high stakes. To ensure a balanced representation according to the type of school two private schools from each category thus primary and secondary formed the sample.

5.2 Selection target of the sample

A stratified random sample of teachers and students from five secondary and five primary schools in the larger Kakamega District formed the sample. The teachers were selected according to the five academic departments, that is languages, mathematics, science, technical/applied and humanities. This is in line with the variation in the teaching methods in each, which might be affected differently in the context of high stakes test. Scholars (specialists in psychometrics) responded to questionnaires in order to provide data on the implications of high stakes in the Kenyan context.

5.3 Data collection instruments

There were three sets of questionnaires to be filled on the basis of the objectives. Students filled questionnaire to provide information on the various effects of high stakes testing. Documentation on high stakes testing was sampled for analysis to ascertain the nature, context and characteristics of high stakes, the opinions of teachers and other educators in a variety of contexts, this included documents on research on the impact of the Massachusetts high stakes test by Luna Catherine and documents on distortion of teaching and testing by Madaus. F. among others by the American education research.

5.4 Pilot study and validation of data collection instruments

The questionnaire was piloted with five teachers and five students not in the sample. The teachers made comments on the questionnaire, whether there were any ambiguous questions to be removed from the list and or replaced. .

5.5 Description of research instruments

There was a Likert scale matrix with items according to the objectives stated and the researcher analyzed the content from secondary data. The teacher questionnaire comprised five sections. In the first section questions eliciting information about the teachers background; their teaching experience, subject areas and how they organize their teaching a head of summative assessment.

The questionnaire here included questions on the characteristics of high stakes testing. This meant that they indicated the use for which test scores are put ranging from rewards, merit pay, accountability standards, tools for education, whether decisions made from high stakes tests improve instruction in class, are used for selection to university, for licensing and employment, program evaluation, sanctions for probation and dismissal amongst other contexts.

The teachers and opinions were determined from their responses on the nature and context of high stakes testing.

5.6 Data collection: The administration

The teachers, students and scholar questionnaire were administered in person to check bias from ambiguous items and clarify on technical terms the respondents would not be familiar with ensure that the questionnaire are returned immediately for immediate data analysis.

5.7 Data analysis of the results

The statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) was handy in order to do analysis descriptively for frequencies and percentages.

6. Results and Discussions

6.1 Demographic information

Majority, 56.5% of the teachers under study were males while 41.3% were females. However, 2.2% of the respondents did not state their age. It was found out that majority, 53.8% of the students were males while 46.2% were females. A majority, 69.2% of the respondents were from the rural background while 23.1% were from the urban. The study shows 43.5% of respondents were between 20-30 years of age while 37% were between 31 – 40 years of age. The majority, 43.5% of the respondents had reached certificate as their education level while 37% had Bachelor's degree as their highest education level. Majority, 52.2% of the respondents had teaching experience of 2 to 10 years while 39.1% had teaching experience of above 10 years.

The study shows that 21.7% of respondents were teaching English/ Literature while 15.2% used to teach Kiswahili subject. However, thirteen percent of the respondents did not respond.

It was also found out that 332.6% of respondents teach in public primary schools while a further 30.4% teach in provincial secondary school.

An overwhelming 97.8 of the respondents stated that they prepare students for public examinations while only 2.2% of the respondents stated that they don't prepare students for examinations.

Table 1: Preparation of candidates for examinations

Preparation of candidates for examinations	Frequency	Percent
3-10 months before exams begins	6	13.0
After comprehensively and amicably covering the contents of the syllabus	4	8.7
At the beginning of every year	7	15.2
At the beginning of the term	5	10.9
From Form 1/ Immediately after admission	13	28.3
Form 3, 3 rd term	1	2.2
Immediately they join Form 4	3	6.5
In lower classes before the examination classes	1	2.2
Regular teaching and revision and discussion groups	1	2.2
No response	5	10.9
Total	46	100.9

Most teachers prepare their students since form one or immediately they are admitted in the school, this was according to 28.3% of the respondents while 15.2% stated that they prepare the students at the beginning of the year.

6.2 How to prepare students

Most respondents stated that they prepare their students by completely covering the syllabus early and through regular testing and assessment on every topic covered to evaluate students. Further, respondents also stated that they do mass revisions by forming groups and offering remedial classes for weak students as well as guiding them through more research work and on how to answer questions. The groups are

formed according to ability of the students for assistance. Respondents also ensure that there are adequate revision materials assigned to the students and they are able to access past papers. The respondents also allow consultations and give private assignments. Some also invite examiners to talk to students as well as participating in symposiums and conducting subject days. They also avoid absenteeism of students so that they attend all classes for the timely coverage syllabus. A number of respondents also stated that they prepare their students for public examinations by motivating them.

Table 2: Implications of high stakes testing on learning

Implications of high stakes testing	Yes		Sometimes		No		No response	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Learners are not able to reproduce knowledge acquired after school period	3	30	5	50	2	20	-	-
Learners are not able to apply knowledge acquired	3	30	4	40	3	30	-	-
There is lack of predictive validity of learning	6	60	4	40	-	-	-	-
Focus is more on what will be tested	5	50	3	30	2	20	-	-
Teacher teaches to the test	6	60	3	30	1	10	-	-
There is a problem of efficiency as teachers teach more on drilling	4	40	5	50	1	10	-	-
Failure of student results in teacher being termed as failure	5	50	4	40	1	10	-	-

The table above ought to show the implications of high stakes testing on learning policy. Majority, 50% of the respondents stated that learners sometimes are not able to reproduce knowledge acquired after school period while 40% agreed that learners are not able to reproduce knowledge acquired after school period due to high stakes testing. A further 40% of the respondents stated that sometimes learners are not able to apply knowledge acquired while 30% agreed that learners are not able to apply knowledge acquired due to high stakes testing, a similar percentage stated that learners are able to apply the knowledge.

The study further shows that there is lack of predictive validity of learning; this was according to 60% of the respondents while 40% stated that sometimes there is lack of predictive validity of learning. Another implication of high stakes testing is that focus is more on what will be tested; this was revealed by 50% of the respondents while 30% stated that sometimes focus is more on what will be tested. Moreover, 60% of the respondents revealed that teacher teaches to the test while 30% stated that sometimes they do teach to the test. Another implication of high stakes testing is that sometimes there are problems of efficiency as teachers teaches more on drilling; this was according to 50% of the respondents while 40% stated that there is quite a problem of efficiency. Fifty percent of the respondents also revealed that failure of students results in teacher being termed as failure while 40% stated that this only happens sometimes.

According to 38.5% of the respondents examinations oftenly cause fear because of the consequences one will face while 26.9% stated that rarely cause fear. Majority, 73.1% of the respondents stated that they remember what they have read even when they do not have exams while 26.9% stated that they do remember what they have read

even when they do not have exams. Further, 46.2% of the respondents agreed that examinations allow one to answer questions using own knowledge and just what the teachers has taught while 30.8% stated that sometimes examinations allow one to do so. Moreover, 42.3% of the respondents revealed that the teachers do not teach everything in the text books that they use while according to 34.6% of the respondents teachers sometimes do not teach everything the text books that they use. However, an overwhelming 84.6% of the respondents stated that examinations are good and should not be done away with while only 7.7% stated that examinations are not good.

Table 3: Implications of high-stakes testing on learning and policy

Implications of high stakes testing	Yes		Sometimes		No		No response	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Learners are not able to reproduce knowledge acquired after school period	3	30	5	50	2	20	-	-
Learners are not able to apply knowledge acquired	3	30	4	40	3	30	-	-
There is lack of predictive validity of learning	6	60	4	40	-	-	-	-
Focus is more on what will be tested	5	50	3	30	2	20	-	-
Teacher teaches to the	6	60	3	30	1	10	-	-

7. Conclusions

The results can be summarized as follows; the conclusion of this study is in accordance with the four objectives.

In terms of psychometrics the following was established;

- The results show that those in education do not perceive that important rewards or sometimes are tied directly to test performance.
- That various decisions are not linked to performance but to individuals or institutions.
- As a result, they do not inform instruction, guidance classification, and licensure.
- The tests are not used to monitor learning.
- The tests and the way they are used increases assessment inequality other than objectivity
- There is need to review the global trends as well as nature of assessment in Kenya so that tests are not used as a mechanism in a single defined assessment and a consequence for pass and failure, it is time to tailor exams to contribute to performance towards socio-economic equitable and performance related conditions.

8. Recommendations

There is need to strengthen national assessment so that the result on the tests to monitor the system, holding the teachers accountable for poor performance. This implies that the test will not be a quantitative indicator of performance, thus checking on malpractices associated with distortion for example cheating, impersonation and others,

if more than one major test would be used to gauge the learners achievement, the impact high stakes have to learning will reduce.

There is need for policy to recognize other areas of achievement by the learner other than centering performance on the KCSE and KCPE scores.

There is need to establish whether resources are sufficient in a given context so as to avoid holding teachers and others accountable even in circumstances when the situation is uncontrollable, one needs enough resources for better performance. Examination bodies must minimize unreliability by ensuring that tests measure what they are intended to.

There is need to device ways to encourage teachers to be creative and innovative in their teaching and do self-appraisal to define their goal. Instead of comparing performance to other teachers, the teacher should do own prior assessment.

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